

Masai

also known as “Maasai”, “Ilmaasai”

Data source: eHRAF

By Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

Entry tags: Religion, African Religions

The Masai are nomadic pastoralists living in parts of what is now Kenya and Tanzania. This entry focuses around the year 1900, when northern Masailand fell under British control, and southern Masailand fell under German control. At this time, the Masai were known as a strong military force, and lived in villages based on an age-grade system. Lineages formed the most important social unit, and groups of lineages comprised clans. Religious and civil leaders inherited their positions through membership in high-ranking lineages. The Masai religious beliefs are centered on an omnipotent, omniscient, and omnipresent supreme high god, 'Ng ai. Because the Masai religion permeates so many aspects of their culture, it is best considered coterminous with the society.

Date Range: 1875 CE - 1915 CE

Region: Southeast Africa

Region tags: Africa, Eastern Africa, Kenya, United Republic of Tanzania

The Masai occupy a region in East Africa, which, at the time of this entry, fell under British and German control with the Anglo-German Agreement of 1886. The British crown colony included what is now modern Kenya, and the German protectorate included what is now modern mainland Tanzania. This entry focuses on the Kisonko or Southern Masai of Tanzania ca. 1875-1915.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=f112-000>

– Source 1 Description: Spencer, P. (1996). Culture Summary: Maasai. New Haven, Conn.: HRAF.

– Source 2 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=f112-018>

- Source 2 Description: Merker, M. (1910). Masai: Ethnographic Monograph Of An East African Semite People. Berlin: Dietrich Reimer (Ernst Vohsen).
- Source 3 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=fl12-013>
- Source 3 Description: Huntingford, G. W. B. (1953). Southern Nilo-Hamites. Ethnographic Survey Of Africa, East Central Africa. London: International African Institute.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.britannica.com/place/eastern-Africa>
- Source 1 Description: Low, D. A., and Marcua, H. G. (2015, February 12). Eastern Africa. Encyclopædia Britannica.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "The first Europeans to become acquainted with the Masai were the missionaries Krapf and Rebmann as long ago as 1848..." (Huntingford, 1953:103).

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: "In 1882 the German naturalist Fischer managed to reach Naivasha, but had to return owing to the hostility of the Masai" (Huntingford, 1953:103). Additionally, "early attempts at missionary work among the Masai were not successful, except among the Il-Arusa (ibid.).

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (resolved rating), "internal warfare seems to occur every year, but usually only during a particular season". Additionally SCCS Variable 1654 indicates that the society is "not pacified for all or part of the twenty-five year time period". Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (resolved rating), "external warfare seems to occur almost constantly and at any time of the year". Additionally SCCS Variable 1654 indicates that the society is "not pacified for all or part of the twenty-five year time period". Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Notes: Because the Masai are nomadic, it is difficult to estimate the population. The principal ethnographic source, Merker, 1953, does not provide an estimated population figure for the Masai at the time this entry focuses on.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The most outstanding lineage, not only of the 'L aiser tribe, but of the whole Masai people, is the En gidon , because both the family of the chief (ol oiboni) and that of the sorcerer (el goiatek) belong to it" (Merker, 1910:24).

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: "...the firm belief of [the chief, otherwise known as ol oiboni] subjects in his prophetdom and in his supernatural ability of sorcery gives him an influence over the destinies of the people" (Merker, 1910:24).

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

↳ Powers are inherited:

– Yes

Notes: Merker, 1910:29

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– Yes

Notes: "From the En gidon lineage there are further supplied, as has already been mentioned, the sorcerers or medicine men (ol goiatiki, el goiatek), several of whom live in each district. Their office, too, is handed down from father to son, who, however, is usually initiated into the whole secret art only after his marriage" (Merker, 1910:29).

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

Notes: The positions of chief (ol oiboni), sorcerer (el goiatek) and medicine man (ol goiatiki) are hereditary (Merker, 1910:29).

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Notes: "The most outstanding lineage, not only of the 'L aiser tribe, but of the whole Masai people, is the En gidon , because both the family of the chief (ol oiboni) and that of the sorcerer (el goiatek) belong to it. The designation "chief" is actually not quite correct, since the ol oiboni does not rule directly and does not exercise any real executive power. He rules only indirectly; the firm belief of his subjects in his prophetdom and in his supernatural ability of sorcery gives him an influence over the destinies of the people" (Merker, 1910:24).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– I don't know

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 66 indicates that there are no large or impressive structures present among the Masai (Murdock and Wilson, 1972; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 66 indicates that there are no large or impressive structures present among the Masai (Murdock and Wilson, 1972; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: No evidence for the presence of pilgrimages were found in any of the ethnographic sources.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "Into the other world (en gatambó = cloud land, i.e., the land where the clouds come from) go the souls of all the deceased..." (Merker, 1910:269).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "Into the other world (en gatambó = cloud land, i.e., the land where the clouds come from) go the souls of all the deceased, both those of the Masai and of non-Masai, both those of the good and those of the bad people" (Merker, 1910:269).

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "As soon as a soul reaches the portal of the other world, which lies far to the north (Kopekob), God decides its future fate. The souls of good people gain entry into paradise, which is equipped with all the beauties and splendors of nature. Lush pastures with fat cattle alternate with lakes, rivers, and cool glades whose trees bear the most delicious fruits. In the midst of this splendor the good souls live in human fashion, but without care, trouble, or work. Every day they receive the best food in abundance. Here, however, in accordance with God's command, each one may marry only one wife. The other world, like the earth, is divided into individual lands, each of which is intended for the souls of one people, so that the person who arrives there will find his deceased relatives. Bad human beings are denied this paradise; they are driven into a barren, waterless desert. Those not so bad also gain entry into paradise through God's grace, though not to live in carefree happiness, but to do hard work" (Merker, 1910:269).

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: "...the other world, which lies far to the north (Kopekob)..." (Merker, 1910:269).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Yes

Notes: "Into the other world (en gatambó = cloud land, i.e., the land where the clouds come from) go the souls of all the deceased..." (Merker, 1910:269).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for details.

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: No evidence for the presence of cremation was found in any ethnographic source.

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No evidence for the presence of mummification was found in any ethnographic source.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "In contrast to the simple exposure of the corpse, that of a chief (ol oiboni), of a married man of the El kiboron lineage, and often also that of a sorcerer (ol goiatiki) is buried" (Merker, 1910:265).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

Notes: "The bottom of a pit a meter deep is covered with a neat's hide moistened with fat, and upon this the corpse is laid in the position described above" (Merker, 1910:265).
Position described: "The corpse is laid on its left side with the head toward the north, so that the face is turned toward the east. The legs are drawn up and lie one upon the other. The left arm is drawn up in such a way that the hand lies close in front of the head, whereas the right arm is bent at the elbow in a right angle; the upper arm rests on the abdomen of the dead man, the hand touches the ground in front of it" (Merker, 1910:264).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– No

Notes: (Merker, 1910:264-5)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

Notes: (Merker, 1910:264-5)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

– No

Notes: "If the laid-out corpse is immediately devoured the first night by hyenas, this is regarded as a sign from 'Ng ai [superior high god], at whose command the animals act here, that the deceased was a good human being. On the other hand, if one finds the corpse still untouched

the next morning, the survivors bring a black ram as a sacrifice to appease the wrathful god. No prayer is spoken in this connection" (Merker, 1910:265).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No evidence for the presence of cannibalism was found in any ethnographic source.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– Yes

Notes: "If the laid-out corpse is immediately devoured the first night by hyenas, this is regarded as a sign from 'Ng ai [superior high god], at whose command the animals act here, that the deceased was a good human being. On the other hand, if one finds the corpse still untouched the next morning, the survivors bring a black ram as a sacrifice to appease the wrathful god. No prayer is spoken in this connection" (Merker, 1910:265).

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1850, Secondary Bone/Body Treatment: Original Scale, indicates that "secondary contact with the body or bones of the deceased does not occur" (Schroeder, 2001; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: An animal is sacrificed at the time of an individual's death, and the fat is used to anoint the deceased person. The animal is not sacrificed to accompany burial. (see Merker, 1910:264-165).

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: For the non-elites, the corpse of the deceased is ceremoniously laid outside and left for animal consumption (Merker, 1910:264-265).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

– Yes

Notes: The corpses of the elites and religious specialists are buried. For a detailed description of these burial practices, see questions below and Merker, 1910, pages 263-267.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Informal burial grounds

Notes: "In contrast to the simple exposure of the corpse, that of a chief (ol oiboni), of a married man of the El kiboron lineage, and often also that of a sorcerer (ol goiatiki) is buried" (Merker, 1910:265). It is not specified where the bodies are buried other than outside.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "In sharp contrast to the anthropolatry, the worship of departed human spirits, and the polydemonism of the [people of Africa], occurring in all forms and gradations, stands the simple, straightforward monotheism of the Masai" (Merker, 1910:268).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: "Their god is called 'Ng ai and is an incorporeal being, a spirit" (Merker, 1910:268).

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: "The people do not think about his appearance. The making of pictorial or sculptural representations of God would be a sin, according to his commandment given to the Masai" (Merker, 1910:268).

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Yes [specify]: 'Ng ai [the supreme high god] made the El kiboron lineage of the El muleljan tribe the primary bearers of the religious traditions

Notes: "The lineage of the El kiboron of the El muleljan tribe, who, according to the view of all the people, are especially favored by 'Ng ai, the god of the Masai, which has made them primarily the bearers of the religious traditions, require a special discussion. Corresponding to their position with 'Ng ai, they are distinguished by a relative peaceableness. The young warriors, to be sure, also set out on raiding expeditions with the other lineages, but they thereby seem to avoid any unnecessary roughness or brutality, in which the others often compete... God rewards them for their virtue by protecting their herds against predatory animals and thieves..." (Merker, 1910:29).

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: "God is the creator of the world, the earth, and all that it harbors. He governs everything through his will. He is the guardian of the natural and moral order of the

world" (Merker, 1910:268).

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: "God is the creator of the world, the earth, and all that it harbors. He governs everything through his will. He is the guardian of the natural and moral order of the world" (Merker, 1910:268).

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Notes: "God is almighty, omnipresent, omniscient, benign, infinite, eternal" (Merker, 1910:268).

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: "God is almighty, omnipresent, omniscient, benign, infinite, eternal" (Merker, 1910:268).

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: "God is the creator of the world, the earth, and all that it harbors. He governs everything through his will. He is the guardian of the natural and moral order of the world" (Merker, 1910:268).

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: "God is almighty, omnipresent, omniscient, benign, infinite, eternal" (Merker, 1910:268).

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: "God is almighty, omnipresent, omniscient, benign, infinite, eternal" (Merker, 1910:268).

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "God's benevolence forgives human beings a great deal and for a long time. Yet human beings are too weak and sinful, so that God has to punish from time to time for improvement. He then does this through sickness, drought, or cattle epidemics" (Merker, 1910:268).

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: "Elephantiasis scroti (en doreng) is regarded as a punishment of God for incest committed" (Merker, 1910:239).

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

"Indirect causal efficacy" refers to not being seen as consciously, directly and actively intervening in the human world, but their overall well being or general attitude has effects on, e.g., quality of harvest, success in war, health, etc.

– Yes

Notes: See Merker, 1910:271

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "God's benevolence forgives human beings a great deal and for a long time" (Merker, 1910:268).

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "Wind and storm are the raging of a wrathful God" (Merker, 1910:271).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1960 indicates that ghosts are not present (Rosenblatt, Walsh, and Jackson, 1976; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The first-born child of 'Ng ai, the girl Barsai, brings to human beings the greatest benefit, the rain, and thereby shows that God is satisfied with the doings on earth. His eldest son, Ol gurugur, announces through thunder and lightning that God is angry with human beings because of their bad behavior and at the same time admonishes them to improve" (Merker, 1910:271). Additionally, "in their journey through life God protects the Masai through guardian angels, who are pictured as winged, invisible beings of human form" (Merker, 1910:269).

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

"Indirect causal efficacy" refers to not being seen as consciously, directly and actively intervening in the human world, but their overall well being or general attitude has effects on, e.g., quality of harvest, success in war, health, etc.

– Yes

Notes: "The first-born child of 'Ng ai, the girl Barsai, brings to human beings the greatest benefit, the rain, and thereby shows that God is satisfied with the doings on earth. His eldest son, Ol gurugur, announces through thunder and lightning that God is angry with human beings because of their bad behavior and at the same time admonishes them to improve" (Merker, 1910:271).

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Protection

Notes: "In their journey through life God protects the Masai through guardian angels, who are pictured as winged, invisible beings of human form...The angel accompanies the person always and everywhere and protects him from dangers, so that he will not succumb in the struggle for existence before the lifetime previously set for him by God has run out; only then does the person die. The angel carries his soul to the other world and then undertakes the protection of a child born on the same day" (Merker, 1910:269).

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: See Merker, 1910:269-271.

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: "The first-born child of 'Ng ai, the girl Barsai, brings to human beings the greatest benefit, the rain, and thereby shows that God is satisfied with the doings on earth. His eldest son, Ol gurugur, announces through thunder and lightning that God is angry with human beings because of their bad behavior and at the same time admonishes them to improve" (Merker, 1910:271).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: "God's benevolence forgives human beings a great deal and for a long time. Yet human beings are too weak and sinful, so that God has to punish from time to time for improvement. He then does this through sickness, drought, or cattle epidemics" (Merker, 1910:268). "The Milky Way is the path along which the children of 'Ng ai wander as bright stars. From here they observe the doings of

mankind and report on them to God" (Merker, 1910:271).

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: See Merker, 1910:287-290.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Notes: "Elephantiasis scroti (en dorengé) is regarded as a punishment of God for incest committed" (Merker, 1910:239).

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Notes: "Elephantiasis scroti (en dorengé) is regarded as a punishment of God for incest committed" (Merker, 1910:239).

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: See Merker, 1910:288-289

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: Merker, 1910:289

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more information on supernatural punishment.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: All examples of supernatural punishment, as described by the principal ethnographer (Merker, 1910), are caused by the high god. Other supernatural beings may punish, such as God's children (Ol gurugur and Barsai), but this is done on the orders of God.

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: All examples of supernatural punishment, as described by the principal ethnographer (Merker, 1910), are caused by the high god. Other supernatural beings may punish, such as God's children (Ol gurugur and Barsai), but this is done on the orders of God.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for specific explanations of supernatural punishment.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: "God's benevolence forgives human beings a great deal and for a long time. Yet human beings are too weak and sinful, so that God has to punish from time to time for improvement. He then does this through sickness, drought, or cattle epidemics" (Merker, 1910:268).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "As soon as a soul reaches the portal of the other world, which lies far to the north (Kopekob), God decides its future fate. The souls of good people gain entry into paradise, which is equipped with all the beauties and splendors of nature...Bad human beings are denied this paradise; they are driven into a barren, waterless desert. Those not so bad also gain entry into paradise through God's grace, though not to live in carefree happiness, but to do hard work" (Merker, 1910:269).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Merker, 1910:268

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: "God's benevolence forgives human beings a great deal and for a long time. Yet human beings are too weak and sinful, so that God has to punish from time to time for improvement. He then does this through sickness, drought, or cattle epidemics" (Merker, 1910:268).

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: "Elephantiasis scroti (en doreng) is regarded as a punishment of God for incest committed" (Merker, 1910:239).

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: "God's benevolence forgives human beings a great deal and for a long time. Yet human beings are too weak and sinful, so that God has to punish from time to time for improvement. He then does this through sickness, drought, or cattle epidemics" (Merker, 1910:268).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more details on supernatural rewards.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Notes: All examples of supernatural reward, as described by the principal ethnographer (Merker, 1910), are caused by the high god. Angels protect individuals, but is ultimately at God's command.

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: All examples of supernatural reward, as described by the principal ethnographer (Merker, 1910), are caused by the high god. Angels protect individuals, but is ultimately at God's command.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "As soon as a soul reaches the portal of the other world, which lies far to the north (Kopekob), God decides its future fate. The souls of good people gain entry into paradise, which is equipped with all the beauties and splendors of nature...Bad human beings are denied this paradise; they are driven into a barren, waterless desert. Those not so bad also gain entry into paradise through God's grace, though not to live in carefree happiness, but to do hard work" (Merker, 1910:269).

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: "Lush pastures with fat cattle alternate with lakes, rivers, and cool glades whose trees bear the most delicious fruits. In the midst of this splendor the good souls live in human fashion, but without care, trouble, or work. Every day they receive the best food in abundance. Here, however, in accordance with God's command, each one may marry only one wife. The other world, like the earth, is divided into individual lands, each of which is intended for the souls of one people, so that the person who arrives there will find his deceased relatives" (Merker, 1910:269).

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Notes: (Merker, 1910:269)

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "God is the creator of the world, the earth, and all that it harbors. He governs everything through his will. He is the guardian of the natural and moral order of the world. The laws and commandments that are valid in the life of the people and of the individual are expressions of his will" (Merker, 1910:268).

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "God is the creator of the world, the earth, and all that it harbors. He governs everything through his will. He is the guardian of the natural and moral order of the world. The laws and commandments that are valid in the life of the people and of the individual are expressions of his will" (Merker, 1910:268).

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: "God is the creator of the world, the earth, and all that it harbors. He governs everything through his will. He is the guardian of the natural and moral order of the world. The laws and commandments that are valid in the life of the people and of the individual are expressions of his will" (Merker, 1910:268).

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Notes: "According to the belief of the Masai, circumcision was introduced by a command of God. After circumcision boys and girls are regarded as adults. The former are supposed to be circumcised as soon as they are strong enough for participation in a war expedition, that is, at the age of 12 to 16" (Merker, 1910:79).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: "In case of distress, danger, sickness, or other calamities, all the people pray to God. Otherwise the men say a prayer mostly only on special occasions, whereas the women pray daily, mornings and evenings. Children do not pray at all in some districts, in others only the girls pray, and in still others all children learn it at the age of six to eight, usually through their mother" (Merker, 1910:272).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– I don't know

Notes: Large-scale rituals are present and celebrated, but it is not clear whether participation is mandatory. "Both in order to honor God and at the same time to supplicate him for something, the Masai celebrate feasts at approximately monthly intervals; these usually take place on moonlit evenings, more rarely they start in the morning or early afternoon" (Merker, 1910:274).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

This question refers to the wider society in which the religious group is located.

– A chiefdom

Notes: "Every tribe (en gischomi) is divided...into a number of lineages (ol gelata, el gelat). Among these, in turn, one distinguishes principal lineages (ol gelata kitok) and sublineages (ol gelat' ate). According to the religious legend, the relationship of the three tribes to one another is that of brothers, whereas the lineages of a tribe stand in relation to them as sons to the father" (Merker, 1910:21). "The most outstanding lineage, not only of the 'L aiser tribe, but of the whole Masai people, is the En gidon , because both the family of the chief (ol oiboni) and that of the sorcerer (el goiatek) belong to it. The designation "chief" is actually not quite correct, since the ol oiboni does not rule directly and does not exercise any real executive power. He rules only indirectly; the firm belief of his subjects in his prophetdom and in his supernatural ability of sorcery gives him an influence over the destinies of the people" (Merker, 1910:24). Additionally, the Masai have one level of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is reflective of a petty chiefdom (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: The Masai religious beliefs are "handed down and taught by old men" (Merker, 1910:270).

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Notes: A Government school was not established until about 1923, which is outside the date range this entry covers. See Huntingford, 1953:103.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The Anglo-German Agreement of 1886 divided land in East Africa between Britain (most of modern Kenya) and Germany (modern mainland Tanzania). This agreement split Masailand essentially in half, with the northern area under British control and the southern area under German control. (Low and Marcus, Encyclopædia Britannica, 2015).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20 indicates that there is no food storage among the Masai (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20 indicates that there is no food storage among the Masai (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: The Masai do not practice agriculture, and do not have irrigation. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 207, 232.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 13, Land Transport, indicates that pack animals are primarily used; Variable 14, Routes of Land Transport, indicates that unimproved trails are used (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). This information leads to the assumption that transportation infrastructure is not present or intensified among the Masai.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other

than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 13, Land Transport, indicates that pack animals are primarily used; Variable 14, Routes of Land Transport, indicates that unimproved trails are used (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). This information leads to the assumption that transportation infrastructure is not present or intensified among the Masai.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 90, police are not specialized (code=1); (Tuden and Marshall, 1972; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: The head of the family resolves disputes. See Merker, 1910:279-280 for more details.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: Punishment for crimes is not consistent across the entire Masai society. See Merker, 1910:179-185 for a description of law and the maintenance of order among the Masai.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: "An awareness and understanding of justice are very little developed among the Masai. Therefore only a small number of customary legal provisions exist, which are by no means uniform for all Masai, but rather often enough vary in the different districts" (Merker, 1910:279).

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Notes: See Merker, 1910:98-100

Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

Notes: "According to this, the institution of the age classes together with the existence of the age grades, which were more sharply defined and made more prominent in their meaning by the former, seems so important for the maintenance of a constantly war-ready troop that the

thought obtrudes as to whether that institution did not first become formed out of a striving for such a band of warriors" (Merker, 1910:100).

↳ Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– Yes

Notes: "The strict organization of the Masai war power rests primarily on the institution of the age classes. With circumcision the youth enters the army to perform his -- the universal -- military service, and, to be sure, as ol barnoti . His age class is that of the recruits and usually forms, together with the next higher one, that of the warriors, the peacetime strength of the standing army" (Merker, 1910:98).

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Notes: See Merker, 1910:207-213

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Masai are nomadic pastoralists, relying primarily on cattle, goats, and sheep for subsistence. Hunting provides a supplementary source of subsistence. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232. Additionally, trade with Bantu provides important sources of agriculturally-grown crops such as beans, millet, and maize (Huntingford, 1953:109).

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Pastoralism

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The Masai are nomadic pastoralists, relying primarily on cattle, goats, and sheep for subsistence. Hunting provides a supplementary source of subsistence. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232. Additionally, trade with Bantu provides important sources of agriculturally-grown crops such as beans, millet, and maize (Huntingford, 1953:109).